

AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE W.S.R TO MUTRAGHATA

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Article Received on 27 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 17 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18798111>

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How to cite this Article: Dr. Nisha C.^{*1}, Dr. Madhukeshwar Hegde². (2026). Ayurvedic Perspective on Chronic Kidney Disease W.S.R To Mutraghata. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(5), 308–317.

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a significant global health concern, with rising prevalence and mortality rates.^[1] Studies indicate a rising trend of CKD prevalence in India, with some research showing an increase from 11.12% (2011-2017) to 16.38% (2018-2023). CKD is defined by kidney damage or a sustained reduction in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) below 60 mL/min/1.73 m² for at least three months.^[2] It is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease and can progress to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) requiring costly dialysis or transplantation, often unaffordable for many in India. Early CKD detection is often incidental, highlighting the need for better screening, especially in regions with lower socioeconomic indices.^[3]

Ayurveda offers a holistic approach to kidney health,

emphasizing prevention through lifestyle practices and early management of urinary ailments. Detoxification therapies and *Ayurvedic* formulations are used to protect renal tissues. Even in advanced stages, *Rasayana* drugs aim to rejuvenate kidneys and improve overall vitality.^[4]

The increasing global burden of CKD, particularly in India where access to renal replacement therapy is limited due to cost, has spurred interest in alternative systems of medicine like *Ayurveda*. In *Ayurvedic* perspective, the *Basti* (urinary bladder region) is considered a vital

area. Among the various urinary disorders described, *Mootraukasaada* and *Mootrakshaya* show similarities to the symptoms of CKD. *Ayurveda* emphasizes preventive measures, detoxification, and the use of medicinal plants for managing kidney health.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

1. To evaluate utility of *ayurvedic* science in its management.
2. To explore chronic kidney disease from the perspective of *ayurveda*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This review utilized classical *Ayurvedic* texts, including *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, to analyze kidney-related concepts and management principles. *Mutraghata* is described by *Acharya Sushruta* and later elaborated by *Acharya Madhavakar* in the *Madhavidan* around 700 A.D. It is also mentioned in texts like *Bhavprakash Nighantu*, *Bhaishjyarnavali*, *Sharangdhara Samhita*, and *Yogratnakara*. Contemporary research articles from databases like PubMed and AYUSH portals were also reviewed to gather evidence on *Ayurvedic* therapies for Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD).

Ayurvedic view

The *Basti* (urinary bladder) plays a key role in both urine formation and the elimination of *Kleda* (waste fluids), similar to the kidneys, which help maintain water and electrolyte balance. *Acharya Shushrut* describes urine formation as a continuous process where digested food is transformed into *Dosha*, *Rasa*, *Mutra*, and *Purish* by the action of *Pachak Pitta* and *Samana Vata*. Urine, formed in the *Pakwashya* (large intestine), is transported to the bladder through the *Mutravaha Nadi*, which functions like a river draining into an ocean. The ducts, resembling lateral pores in an earthen pot, continuously fill the bladder. The *Mutravaha Nadi* and *Adhoga Dhamani* can be understood as nephrons and renal arteries, respectively. *Mutraghata*, characterized by *Shoshana* (reduced urine formation) and *Pratihanyata* (obstruction in urine formation), includes conditions like *Mootraukasaada* and *Mootrakshaya*, which mirror symptoms of chronic kidney disease (CKD).

The *Ayurvedic* concept of *Mutraghata*, signifying urinary retention with mild dysuria due to obstruction, holds relevance to CKD. *Sushruta* describes various obstructive conditions under *Mutraghata*, such as *Vata Kundalika* and *VataAshtila*, potentially leading to *Mootraukasaada* (anuria or nephropathy), mirroring obstructive uropathies in modern science progressing to nephropathy. *Charaka*, on the other hand, discusses *Mootradosha*, beginning with

Mootraukasaada, suggesting systemic illnesses like *Prameha* leading to nephropathy, similar to diabetic or hypertensive nephropathy.

Hence *mutraghata* according to *sushruta* depicts -obstructive uropathy ending up in nephropathy.

Mootradosha according to *charaka* depicts- systemic illness ending up in nephropathycondition.^[6]

Mootraukasaada refers to anuria, often seen in CKD, resulting from *Margaavarana* (obstruction of channels) of *Vata Dosha* by *Pitta* or *Kapha* in the *Basti* region. *PittajaVikaras* affecting *bastipradesha* ending up in *mutraukasaasa* like *Prameha* leading to diabetic nephropathy or acute glomerulonephritis can cause *Mootraukasaada*. *KaphajaVikaras* can be understood as conditions like renal artery stenosis leading to nephropathy.^[7]

Mootrakshaya, characterized by oliguria, is described by *Sushruta* as affecting individuals with *RookshaDeha* (chronic debilitating diseases like *Prameha* or hypertension leading to nephropathy) and *KlantaDeha* (acute fulminating illnesses like septicemia leading to nephropathy), *basti* gets affected by *pitta* and *vatadosha* resulting in *mootrakshaya*.^[8]

In CKD stages 1 and 2, symptoms are often asymptomatic and detected via GFR, with initial symptoms described in *Ayurveda* under *Rasa Pradoshaja Vikara*. In stage 3, reduced urine output (*Mootrakshaya*) occurs. In stages 4 and 5, symptoms such as anemia, fatigue, swelling (*Shotha*), loss of appetite, vomiting, and pitting edema (due to electrolyte imbalance) emerge, resembling *Kaphaja Shotha* in *Ayurveda*.

NIDANA

While no specific *Nidana* (causes) for *Mutraghata* are described in *Brihatrayi* and *Laghutrayi*, the *Nidan* for *Mutrakrichhra* can be applied to *Mutraghata*. These include excessive exercise (*Ativyayama*), strong drugs (*Teekshna Aushadha*), excessive alcohol (*Rukshya madya prasanga*), riding on fast-moving vehicles or animals (*Nityadrutya prusthayanat*), consumption of wetland animal flesh (*Anupamasthya*), overeating before digestion (*Adhyashana*), and indigestion (*Ajeernat*).

PROBABLE SAMPRAPTHI OF CKD AND MUTRAGHATA.^[9]

<i>Sanchaya Avastha</i> (Accumulation)	vitiated <i>Apana Vayu</i> accumulating, causing mild, often neglected urinary discomfort, abdominal distension, and gurgling.
<i>PrakopaAvastha</i> (Aggravation)	further <i>Vata</i> vitiation, affecting digestion and leading to early <i>Ama</i> formation, manifesting as sour belching and thirst, without clear urinary symptoms.
<i>PrasaraAvastha</i> (Spreading)	vitiated <i>Doshas</i> spread, complicating diagnosis. <i>Ama</i> formation continues, hindering urine formation by obstructing channels. Symptoms like indigestion, burning sensation, and anorexia appear, alongside increased but still unclear urinary difficulty.
<i>Sthanasamshraya Avastha</i> (Localization)	the lodging of vitiated <i>Doshas</i> and <i>Ama</i> in the <i>Basti</i> ,causing premonitory symptoms like bladder distension, pain, and urinary obstruction, suggesting the onset of specific <i>Mutraghata</i> types.
<i>Vyakta Avastha</i> (Manifestation)	the full spectrum of symptoms for each <i>Mutraghata</i> variety, signifying a clear diagnosis but also potential complications if earlier stages were missed.

In modern medicine, the pathogenesis of chronic kidney disease (CKD) involves damage to renal cells due to various underlying causes, such as immune complex deposition, inflammation from specific types of glomerular nephritis, or toxin buildup in renal tubules and interstitium. The systemic harm is a result of the accumulation of toxins that would typically be excreted by the kidneys, as well as complications arising from the loss of other renal functions, such as maintaining fluid and electrolyte balance, hormone regulation, and the progressive systemic inflammation that affects the vascular and nutritional systems.

PROGNOSIS^[10]

Early CKD (stages 1-2)	<i>Krcchrasādhaya</i>
Stages 3-4	<i>Yāpya</i>
End-stage renal disease (stage 5) with uremic features	<i>Asādhya</i> due to systemic damage and fatal prognosis

RESULT**General Treatment Principles for Mootraghata /CKD**

Primary *Dosha*: *Vatadosha* is the main *dosha* involved and should be the primary focus of treatment.

Individualized Approach: Treatment should consider

- * *Doshadhikya* (predominance of *doshas*).
- * *DoshaSamsarga* (combination of *doshas*).
- * *Margavarana* (obstruction of channels).^[11]

Specific Treatments

- * *Snehana*: Oleation therapy using *Taila* (oil), *Gritha* (ghee).
- * *Swedana*: Sudation therapy using *Upanaha* (poultice) or *Avaghaha* (immersion).
- * *Virechana*: Purgation therapy, specifically *Snehavirechana* (oleation-induced purgation).
- * *Basti*: Enema therapy, specifically *Uttarabasti* (urethral/vaginal enema).^[12]

Specific Disease Management: Treatment should address

- * *Mootra kruchra chikitsa* (treatment of painful urination).
- * *Ashmari chikitsa* (treatment of urinary stones).
- * *Mootra udavarta chikitsa* (treatment of upward flow of urine).
- * *Margavarana Chikitsa (Mootroukasada)* (treatment of obstruction in urinary passages).^[13]

Treatment Principles in the Context of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)

Diseases are categorized as:

1. *Swatantra* (independent/primary).
2. *Paratantra* (dependent/secondary)- 2 types are:
 - a. *Poorvaroopakya* (CKD as a pre-existing/causative condition).
 - b. *Upadravakya* (CKD as a complication of another disease).^[14]

Complex Nature of CKD: CKD can arise from:

- * Disease originating in *Pradhanamarma* (vital points).
- * Disease that is inherently an *Upadravavyadhi* (complication).
- * *Dhatukshaya* (tissue depletion) affecting all *Dhatu*s (tissues) and *Avayava*s (organs).

Simultaneous Treatment: Both the

- * Primary causative illness (*Poorva roopakya vyadhi*).
 - * Manifested secondary illness/effect (*Upadravakya vyadhi* - CKD itself)
- should be treated concurrently.^[15]

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda offers a unique lens to understand CKD through concepts like "*Basti*," "*Mootraukasaada*," and "*Mootrakshaya*," mirroring modern understanding of nephropathies. The progression of "*Mutraghata*" aligns with the insidious decline in kidney function in CKD. *Ayurvedic* pathogenesis, emphasizing *Dosha* imbalances (*Vata*, *Kapha*) and *Dhatu* involvement, resonates with the systemic nature of CKD, including toxin accumulation and

multi-organ effects. The *Ayurvedic* prognosis, categorizing CKD stages by treatability, reflects modern clinical realities. Treatment principles focusing on *Vata* pacification (*Snehana, Swedana, Basti*) and addressing underlying conditions offer potential therapeutic avenues. Recognizing CKD as both a primary and secondary condition underscores the need for holistic management. Integrating *Ayurvedic* insights with modern medicine could provide accessible and cost-effective strategies, especially in resource-limited settings like India, to combat the rising burden of CKD.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic principles demonstrate significant conceptual parallels with the modern understanding of CKD, offering a framework for its pathogenesis and management. Concepts like "*Mootraukasaada*" and the stages of "*Mutraghata*" provide insights into kidney dysfunction. The *Ayurvedic* emphasis on early detection, individualized *Vata*-pacifying treatments, and addressing root causes holds promise for a holistic approach to CKD. Further rigorous research integrating classical *Ayurvedic* knowledge with modern science is crucial to validate the efficacy and safety of specific *Ayurvedic* interventions. This integration could lead to more accessible and affordable alternative or complementary therapies, particularly beneficial in regions with limited access to conventional renal replacement therapy, ultimately aiming to improve outcomes and quality of life for CKD patients in India and globally.

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